

1 **TITLE PAGE**

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3 **A novel approach to evaluate the effects of offshore energy infrastructure on the**
4 **northern Gulf of Mexico shrimp fleet**

5

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28 **STRUCTURED ABSTRACT**

29 **Objective**

30 The existence of offshore energy infrastructure in US federal waters requires an understanding
31 of how artificial structures impact regional fisheries. The Louisiana and Texas continental shelf
32 in the Northwestern Gulf of Mexico has a long history of offshore oil and natural gas
33 development and harbors the penaeid shrimp fishery, the highest-valued commercial fishery in
34 the region. Proposed wind energy areas (WEAs) on the shelf for offshore wind energy may
35 impact this fishery due to spatial overlap with historical shrimping grounds and the fishery's use
36 of bottom trawls.

37 **Methods**

38 We used high-resolution spatio-temporal data on shrimp fishery effort developed from vessel
39 monitoring data to investigate how development of proposed WEAs might impact the shrimp
40 fleet. We quantified patterns of shrimp fishing effort at multiple spatio-temporal scales. We also
41 investigated the attraction and avoidance response by shrimp vessels to existing oil and natural
42 gas rigs to infer how future construction of fixed structures affects the spatial dynamics and
43 behavior of the shrimp fleet.

44 **Results**

45 Less than 2.5% of the total annual shrimping effort between 2015 and 2019 occurred within the
46 proposed WEAs in the region, and while rigs were generally avoided, shrimper trawling behavior
47 was modified in certain regions due to spatial constrictions. The density of rigs largely controlled
48 how closely shrimp vessels operated near platforms. In areas with high rig density, most effort
49 occurred at distances nearly equal to the horizon, suggesting that line of sight was an important
50 factor driving shrimper fishing behavior.

51 **Conclusions**

52 Further consideration of fishing fleet responses to structures will enhance our understanding of
53 how ocean multi-use development will impact regional bottom trawl fisheries and provide insight

54 into the applicability of these methods for future marine spatial planning in this region and
55 beyond.

56

57 **LAY SUMMARY**

58 Offshore rigs affect shrimp trawling behavior on the Louisiana-Texas continental shelf, with
59 vessels generally avoiding rigs but altering trawling in areas with high rig densities.

60 Understanding these responses can assist future marine planning to balance energy
61 development and fisheries sustainability.

62

63 **KEYWORDS**

64 vessel monitoring system, bottom trawl, marine spatial planning, mixed effects regression,
65 spatial ecology, northern brown shrimp (*Farfantepenaeus aztecus*), Atlantic white shrimp

66 (*Litopenaeus setiferus*)

67

68 **1. INTRODUCTION**

69 The global development of offshore energy infrastructure has been rapidly advancing in the past
70 decade from the construction of natural gas and offshore wind (OSW) platforms as a means to
71 diversify energy production and expand Blue Economy initiatives (Gourvenec et al. 2022).

72 Investment in OSW is regarded as a key part of many national and international decarbonization
73 goals (Bhattacharya et al. 2021) and over the past decade has become a factor in US federal

74 and state waters (Haggett et al. 2020). While the former U.S. Executive Branch led by President
75 Biden set a goal of doubling offshore wind production by 2030 (Exec. Ord. No. 14008, 2021),

76 recent actions by the U.S. Executive Branch have put a pause on OSW leasing and have called
77 for more research into the potential impacts of OSW infrastructure (90 Fed. Reg. 8363, Doc.

78 Num. 2025-0166). As of May 2024, the U.S. OSW energy operating capacity was approximately
79 174 megawatts (MW) generated by three projects (Block Island Wind [30 MW], Coastal Virginia

80 Offshore Wind [12 MW], and South Fork Wind [132 MW]) and another 4,097 MW under
81 construction in the U.S. northeast and Mid-Atlantic (McCoy et al. 2024). The effects of the
82 growth of the OSW industry, which is on track to become a major use of marine space and a
83 source of potential obstacles for humans and habitat for biota, are not well understood and vary
84 locally and regionally (Methratta et al., 2023). There is a need to understand the impacts of
85 offshore energy infrastructure including OSW on marine fisheries from a historical perspective
86 and during the planning phase before large-scale operational projects are completed to
87 minimize conflicts among these sectors.

88
89 In previous evaluations of marine space use, a common approach has been to evaluate the
90 historical distribution of harvested species or coarse-scale fishery footprints relative to areas
91 proposed for development to infer potential impacts on fisheries (Gusatu et al., 2020; Randall et
92 al., 2022). However, research on the impacts of offshore infrastructure, particularly OSW
93 development, on fisheries has previously been constrained to analysis of effort, catch, or
94 abundance inside of a proposed wind energy area (WEA) to that outside of the proposed WEA
95 (Randall et al. 2022). Many studies have focused on impacts on socioeconomics and
96 recreational fisheries in prospective or existing OSW areas (Navarro et al., 2022; Smythe et al.,
97 2021; Stelzenmüller et al., 2021; Kirkpatrick et al., 2017) or perceptions about multiple
98 concurrent uses of ocean space (Schupp et al., 2021; Haggett et al., 2020). Other studies
99 speculate about potential fisheries population impacts, but do not conduct quantitative analyses
100 due to insufficient monitoring data (Perry & Heyman, 2020 or Hooper & Austen, 2014).

101 Commonly, studies focus exclusively on impacts on commercially valuable fish species in
102 singular OSW areas (Jech et al., 2023) or using a single species approach (Thatcher et al.,
103 2024; Fayram & de Risi, 2007). Stanley and Wilson (1990) employed a fisheries-dependent
104 approach to examine species composition and relative abundance of fish associated with oil
105 and gas structures in the U.S. Gulf of Mexico (hereafter referred to as the Gulf) from 1987 to

106 1988. Limited research exists on the effects of fixed marine structures on spatiotemporal fishing
107 effort or harvest due to the lack of high-resolution spatial data for most fisheries.

108

109 The effects of WEAs on the distribution of fishing effort are likely a more direct indicator of
110 potential fishery impacts, but the spatial dynamics of mobile fishing vessels are not widely
111 available and thus rarely considered. Therefore, information about the effects of fixed structures
112 on the spatiotemporal dynamics of fisheries is rare. The effects of WEAs may vary spatially and
113 temporally due to the typically high spatiotemporal heterogeneity that characterizes seasonally
114 prosecuted and highly mobile fishing fleets. Inside vs. outside analyses are limited because they
115 (1) implicitly assume (future) behavioral responses that have not been observed and (2) do not
116 consider potential impacts of spatial displacement that may occur beyond the boundaries of the
117 proposed WEA. Instead, quantifying the spatio-temporal responses of fishing fleets to current
118 fixed structures in the marine environment could be a useful surrogate for how proposed future
119 structures will likely impact fisheries.

120

121 The penaeid shrimp fishery is the highest-valued commercial fishery and has the second most
122 commercial landings in the Gulf (NMFS, 2024). Landings are dominated by three species of
123 shrimp: northern brown shrimp (*Farfantepenaeus aztecus*), Atlantic white shrimp (*Litopenaeus*
124 *setiferus*), and northern pink shrimp (*Farfantepenaeus duorarum*). The potential WEAs on the
125 Louisiana-Texas (LA-TX) continental shelf in the northwestern Gulf overlaps with the
126 distributions of brown shrimp and white shrimp, which are found in abundance in shallow
127 (inshore) to medium depths (about 150 meters) on the LA-TX shelf (Montero et al. 2016). Pink
128 shrimp can be found in the southern TX shelf but are primarily distributed off the Gulf coast of
129 Florida (Etzold and Cristmas, 1977). Brown and white shrimp dominate the LA-TX penaeid
130 fishery, with white shrimp generally occupying shallower habitats (Zimmerman and Nance,
131 2001) and brown shrimp occupying shallow-to-medium depth temperate waters (Etzold and

132 Christmas, 1977) with abundant oxygen (Renaud, 1986). The Gulf shrimp fleet has been outfitted
133 with vessel monitoring systems (VMS) since the early 2000s, allowing for detailed tracking of
134 their movement throughout the Gulf.

135

136 The seasonal variability of Gulf shrimp fishery effort is partially driven by the timing of the annual
137 Texas closure, which typically occurs May 15 through July 15 (GMFMC, 1981). During this time,
138 state and federal waters are closed to all shrimp fishing to allow newly recruiting shrimp to grow
139 to larger sizes and thus contribute to higher ex-vessel revenues and reduced discards (Griffin et
140 al. 1993). The closure of waters off Texas has the regional effect of concentrating brown and
141 white shrimping effort off the Alabama, Mississippi, and Louisiana coasts. In the weeks before
142 the opener, vessels will return to port to offload, restock supplies, and steam to Texas federal
143 waters for what essentially is a fishing derby (Nance et al. 1991). This fervor of shrimping
144 activity lasts a few weeks to a month before the fleet redistributes across the LA-TX shelf. There
145 is some flexibility by the shrimp fishery participants to switch between species (i.e., brown, pink,
146 and white) because the trawling gear is similar, and as a result, the regional distribution of
147 shrimping effort is a function of the seasonal distribution of shrimp species. A portion of federally
148 permitted shrimp vessels spend some of the time during the winter months fishing for pink
149 shrimp northwest of the Florida Keys (Scott-Denton et al. 2012).

150

151 The industrial evolution of the LA-TX shelf has progressed since the mid-twentieth century,
152 adding structure to the otherwise relatively flat continental shelf. The extensive offshore oil and
153 natural gas (ONG) industry on the LA-TX shelf may be used to infer potential impacts of OSW
154 development on the shrimp fleet distribution due to the similar nature of the structures. From
155 1947 to 2023, 7165 documented rig structures and other infrastructure including well heads and
156 pipelines were constructed across the LA-TX shelf (Yergin, 1991; Shipp and Bortone, 2009;
157 BOEM, 2024). The construction, space occupied, and eventual decommissioning of these

158 platforms have affected and been affected by recreational, subsistence, and commercial fishing
159 activities, most notably the culturally and economically significant penaeid shrimp fishery (Priest,
160 2016). The underwater structures of the rigs are ecologically diverse and biologically productive
161 (Kaier & Pulsipher, 2005; Shulze et al. 2020) functioning similarly to artificial reefs. Whether the
162 rigs are active or decommissioned and turned into artificial reefs, they are frequently visited by
163 recreational fishermen and divers, significantly contributing to the recreational economy in a
164 region (Brashier, 1988; Gordon, 1993; Kaiser & Pulsipher, 2005).

165
166 Starting in 2021, the U.S. Department of Interior began exploring the viability of OSW
167 infrastructure development in the federal waters of the Gulf (DOI, 2021). Throughout the siting
168 and environmental assessment phases of exploration, the Bureau of Ocean Energy
169 Management (BOEM), with the support of NOAA National Centers for Coastal and Ocean
170 Science (NCCOS), conducted spatial suitability modeling (hereafter NCCOS/BOEM suitability
171 model, or NBSM) to determine optimal locations for future WEAs in the Gulf. The initial round of
172 analyses resulted in 14 suitable WEAs (Randall et. al., 2022), and the approach has since been
173 expanded to other basins in the U.S. EEZ being considered for OSW development. Following
174 assessment and public comment, BOEM selected two Gulf WEAs for the first round of
175 advancement, leading to a public lease offering of 3 areas within those blocks. In August 2023,
176 BOEM held the first-ever OSW energy lease auction in the Gulf in the Federal Waters off of
177 Texas and Louisiana, resulting in one lease to RWE Inc. (DOI, 2023).

178
179 Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) is an approach to organizing uses of marine space and has
180 been used for numerous offshore development activities on the LA-TX shelf; however, the sheer
181 number of sectors—including oil and gas extraction, economically important fisheries, and
182 shipping activities—and planning efforts have resulted in an overall negative impression of MSP
183 by stakeholders in the region (Collier, 2013). Due to the historic use of the LA-TX shelf by the

184 shrimp fishery, there was a concern that any OSW development may adversely impact the
185 fishery due to the potential spatial overlap of the two industries (Randall et al., 2022). The
186 NBSM included spatial patterns of shrimping effort as one of several human-use, biological, and
187 political factors aggregated across seasonal and annual time scales to identify areas that
188 minimize multi-use conflicts. The development of additional offshore infrastructure creates
189 inherent trade-offs as structures may limit the types of fishing gear due to operational hazards
190 but refuge effects may translate into spillover boosting overall population productivity (Craig &
191 Link, 2023). The specific impacts of offshore infrastructure such as OSW farms in the region are
192 not fully understood and new offshore infrastructure must compete for space with existing
193 industries.

194

195 This paper's overarching objective was to understand how the offshore infrastructure affects the
196 shrimp fishery on the LA-TX shelf. Evaluating the potential effects of OSW on marine capture
197 fisheries requires information on the likely responses of fishing fleets to fixed artificial structures
198 in the environment. Our goal was to analyze the spatial scale at which shrimp vessels respond
199 to offshore oil rigs during normal fishing operations to gain insight into the effects that structure
200 has on shrimping effort and thus infer how the fleet might respond to OSW. Our study approach
201 was broadly divided into two research directions. First, we quantify spatio-temporal patterns of
202 shrimp effort inside vs. outside the currently proposed WEAs at multiple spatial (0.5 km to shelf-
203 wide) and temporal (seasonal to annual) scales to understand how proposed WEAs may impact
204 the fishery. Second, we analyze the spatial responses of shrimp vessels to existing oil rigs in the
205 Gulf at different spatial scales to infer how fixed structures in the marine environment affect the
206 spatial dynamics of the shrimp fleet.

207

208 2. METHODS

209 2.1 DATA

210 2.1.1 Shrimp Fishery Effort

211 The shrimp fishery effort estimation method described here used the same raw vessel
212 monitoring system (VMS) data as was used for the NBSM (Randall et al., 2022), as well as prior
213 studies (Gallaway et al 2003a; Gallaway et al 2003b; Purcell et al. 2017). For our analyses, an
214 algorithm developed by Dettloff (2024) determined shrimping effort in hours fished as described
215 here. Raw position pings were filtered to retain pings within the Gulf less than a specific depth
216 (150 m), and vessel speed was calculated using time and distance traveled. Pings with
217 unrealistic speeds (> 21.3 kph or 11.5 knots) were removed, and vessel speeds less than 1.9
218 knots were considered stopping or idling. Effort was identified as consecutive pings at trawling
219 speed (3.5 to 6.6 kph or 1.9 to 3.6 knots) for a minimum of one hour with a minimum transition
220 time of 10 minutes between trawling activities. Shrimp vessels were selected for the VMS
221 program using a spatially stratified random sample weighted toward vessels with more landings
222 in the years before selection. The randomized nature of the federal VMS program vessel
223 selection process lends support to our assumption that the spatial distribution of the VMS data
224 within strata is representative of the federally permitted shrimp fleet.

225

226 2.1.2 Wind Energy Areas

227 The NBSM identified 14 WEAs consisting of 2,398,150 acres (9705 km²) of suitable ocean area,
228 with WEAs ranging in size from 39,836 ac to 546,645 ac (161 km² to 2212 km², Randall et al.,
229 2022). The total area that was considered in the suitability model was 29,693,940 ac (120,167
230 km²). The 14 potential WEAs on the LA-TX shelf represent about 6% of the area typically
231 trawled by shrimp vessels with the majority in Texas federal waters (Fig. 1). Each WEA contains
232 at least 7 potential lease blocks based on the space needed to produce an economically viable
233 amount of energy (Randall et al., 2022). The shapefiles for the WEAs, the RWE lease block

234 (awarded in August 2023, within WEA M), and other lease areas currently being considered in
235 the public sale notice as of December 2024 (within WEAs C and D) were accessed directly from
236 NCCOS (Fig. 1; BOEM, 2024). Shrimp trawling activity was one of about 75 data layers
237 considered; other layers included military operating areas, other commercial fishing activity,
238 protected species distributions, vessel traffic and shipping fairways, marine protected areas, and
239 oil and natural gas leases, among others. The NBSM identified shrimp trawling activity using
240 raw VMS data from January 1, 2015 to December 31, 2019, binned to a 100 x 100 m grid,
241 summed per day, and the mean days trawled per year was calculated. Cells with more than 4.5
242 mean days of active trawling were considered unsuitable for OSW development due to
243 “moderate to high” shrimping effort (Randall et. al., 2022).

244

245 **2.1.3 BOEM Platform Data**

246 Data on the offshore ONG infrastructure on the LA-TX shelf were obtained from BOEM's data
247 repository (BOEM, 2024). We limited our analysis to the platform structure database, which is a
248 comprehensive list of all offshore rigs located within the outer continental shelf of the Gulf,
249 stretching the U.S. exclusive economic zone (i.e., 12 nautical miles territorial sea to 200 nmi
250 offshore). The platform database contains coordinates, installation date, removal date, site
251 clearance date, structure type, water depth, and if the structure is connected to other platforms
252 by a walkway (<https://www.data.boem.gov/Platform/PlatformStructures/FieldDefinitions.aspx>).

253 To match the shrimp VMS data, we retained rigs constructed before the year of matching VMS
254 data and removed rigs listed as cleared before the year of interest. Additionally, we counted rigs
255 attached by a walkway as one structure.

256

257 **2.2 ANALYSIS**

258 **2.2.1 Spatio-temporal patterns in shrimping effort**

259 We restricted our analyses to shrimp effort within the Louisiana-Texas continental shelf,
260 statistical zones (StatZones) 13-21 (hereafter referred to the LA-TX shelf), where WEAs are
261 proposed and the majority of the shrimp fishing has been conducted (Fig. 1). Only the years
262 from 2015 to 2019 were used for analysis because data limitations precluded the use of pre-
263 2015 and post-2019 data. The total number of self-reported shrimp vessels active per year
264 (Smith et al. 2023) was used to calculate the proportion of the shrimp fleet with VMS installed.
265 Shrimp vessel activity was aggregated to assess the spatiotemporal patterns of shrimping effort
266 and the number of vessels in both StatZones and WEAs per month and per year. We use
267 StatZone as a consistent unit of spatial aggregation because they are the spatial zones in which
268 shrimp effort and landings have historically been reported (Patella 1975). Total effort (hours
269 trawled) was summed per year for each StatZone, and median vessel effort was calculated per
270 month per StatZone. The corresponding quantities were also calculated for each WEA. The
271 effort per month for both StatZones and WEAs were divided by the area of interest in square
272 kilometers to obtain effort density (hours per km²) to easily compare between areas (i.e., SZ and
273 WEA).

274

275 **2.2.2 Shrimping Effort Near Oil Rigs**

276 We performed several analyses to assess the spatial scale at which shrimp vessels engage in
277 fishing operations near rigs. The first analysis applied a series of circular buffers differing in size
278 (i.e., 0.5, 1, 2, 3, 5, 7.5, 10, 12.5, 15, 17.5, 20, 25, 30, 40 km) around each ONG rig and then
279 summed the shrimping effort (hours spent trawling) within each buffer per StatZones (Fig. 1) by
280 year. These summations were then converted to proportions by dividing by the total effort within
281 each StatZone per year. We also summed all the vessels that spent any amount of time fishing
282 in the same buffers to capture the proportion of the instrumented vessels that approached rigs

283 within the respective buffer during trawling. When the size of the buffer was large enough to
284 touch another buffer, the summation was a union of the buffers so that the summation of effort
285 was not duplicative. The shrimp effort was subsetting for federal waters, 3 (LA) or 9 (TX) nautical
286 miles (5.6 or 16.7 km, respectively) from shore to the 150 m isobath, which represents the limit
287 of shelf fished by the shrimp industry for penaeid shrimp species. Buffers were also clipped to
288 the StatZones of interest and federal waters to prevent counting effort outside the StatZones.

289

290 We also performed a series of randomization analyses to assess the association between
291 shrimping effort and the distribution of rigs. First, a random sample of VMS pings ($n = 90,000$ or
292 $10,000$ per StatZone) were selected, and then quantified the number of rigs within the buffer
293 distances listed above from each point. We then repeated the analysis by selecting random
294 points ($n = 90,000$ or $10,000$ per StatZone), and then quantified the number of rigs within the
295 buffer distances to estimate a null distribution. The difference in rig encounter rate between the
296 subsampled VMS data and random points approximates avoidance or attraction behavior. The
297 results of these analyses will be referred to as the rig encounter metric.

298

299 We did not know the spatial scales over which shrimp vessels are able to locate and potentially
300 respond to rigs. As a result, we developed a method to approximate which of the spatial scales
301 (i.e., buffers) described earlier are potentially most relevant to shrimpers. We then calculated
302 several line-of-sight distances to put the buffer analysis into a context relevant to the shrimp
303 fleet. These distances are based on an estimate of how far the horizon would be as observed
304 from the wheelhouse of a shrimp vessel. We also calculated several distances slightly beyond
305 the horizon as rigs are tall structures that can still be seen if they are over the horizon. Distance
306 to the horizon was calculated as:

307

308

$$Dh = \sqrt{2 * Re * hw}$$

309 (Equation 1)

310 Where Dh is the distance to the horizon from the shrimp vessel, Re is the radius of the earth,
311 which was assumed to be 6,367.45 km, and hw is the height of the wheelhouse, which was
312 assumed to be 15 ft (4.572×10^{-3} km). We also calculated the distance between the shrimp
313 vessel and a partly visible rig and when just the very top was visible. The latter assumes that the
314 rig has a light at its peak and is visible primarily at night when most shrimp trawling occurs.
315 These distances were calculated as:

316

$$317 \quad Db = Dh + \sqrt{2 * Re * hr}$$

318 (Equation 2)

319 Where Db is the distance between the shrimp vessels and rigs, Dh is Equation 1, and hr is the
320 height of the rig, which was assumed to be 150 ft (4.572×10^{-2} km). The rig height was multiplied
321 by one-third and one-half to get the distance at which the top two-thirds and top half were
322 visible, respectively, and the full height was used to calculate the distance when just the top of
323 the rig was visible. These distances equalled 7.6, 21.6, 24.7, and 31.8 km for the horizon, top
324 two-thirds, top half, and just the top being visible, respectively. These calculations neglect what
325 can be seen on radar and electronic charts and we assumed that sight is the primary driver of
326 shrimp vessel behavior during trawling around rigs. Additionally, these calculations assume
327 perfect conditions and disregard sea state such as wave height and any refraction effects that
328 can further affect visibility.

329

330 **2.2.3 Response of Shrimpers to Rigs**

331 To further characterize the response of shrimpers to fixed structures, we analyzed the change in
332 shrimping effort before versus after the removal of oil rigs at two spatial scales (1 km and 7.5
333 km). These two distances were chosen to capture effort at relatively small scales and relatively
334 large scales to cover a range of decision-making timeframes. A shrimp boat will move 1 km in

335 approximately 15 minutes moving at 4.63 kph (2.5 knots a typical trawling speed); whereas a
336 shrimp boat will reach the horizon (7.5 km) in approximately 1 hour and 40 minutes if moving in
337 a straight line. We expected effort to be higher in the year after removal compared to the year
338 before removal if fixed structures (e.g., oil rigs) significantly alter the spatial distribution of
339 shrimping effort. The original intent of this research was to examine changes in shrimp effort in
340 response to the construction of new rigs on the LA-TX shelf as a proxy for OSW farm
341 construction. However, preliminary investigations showed that only 6 ONG rigs were installed
342 during the period of our analysis (i.e., 2015-2019; BOEM, 2024). Filtering for removals that had
343 effort in the years before and after (2016, 2017, and 2018), only 2 rigs remained for analysis.
344 We therefore decided to characterize changes in shrimp effort before and after the removals of
345 rigs to gain insight into how fixed structures affect the spatial dynamics of the shrimp fleet.

346
347 We compared shrimp effort within a rig removal site in the year prior and the year post-removal
348 using generalized linear mixed-effects regression models (GLMMs). We filtered the data to
349 include rigs removed in the years of interest (2016, 2017, and 2018), applied a buffer around
350 each rig, and summed the effort in the year prior and the year after removal (referred to as
351 treatment and coded as pre and post-removal). Effort during the year of removal was not
352 included in the calculations because we assumed there would be a lag between removal and
353 shrimpers taking advantage of new territory. Total effort was summed by StatZone pre- and
354 post-removal and included in models as a fixed effect to control for overall differences in effort
355 between years. The data were filtered using a 1 km buffer and a 7.5 km buffer (the horizon
356 distance) and modeled separately. Shrimp effort near rigs was highly right-skewed with some
357 mass at zero. Thus, effort was assumed to follow a Tweedie distribution with mean μ and
358 variance $= \phi\mu^p$ where ϕ is the dispersion parameter and p the power parameter, both estimated
359 by maximum likelihood. Fixed effects included StatZone (categorical with eight levels), total
360 StatZone effort (continuous), and treatment (categorical with two levels; pre-removal and post-

361 removal). The interaction terms were StatZone x total StatZone effort and treatment x StatZone.
362 We modeled complexID (a unique identifier for each rig complex) as a random effect to account
363 for the non-independence of observations obtained from the same rig complex removal site.

364 The GLMM was defined as follows:

365

366 $\text{Effort}_{ijk} \sim \text{Tweedie}(\mu_{ijk})$

367 $\log(\mu_{ijk}) \sim \text{StatZone}_i + \text{TotalEffortSZ}_{ij} + \text{Treatment}_{ijk} + \text{StatZone}_i \times \text{TotalEffortSZ}_{ij} + \text{StatZone}_i \times$
368 $\text{Treatment}_{ijk} + \text{ComplexID}_i$

369 $\text{ComplexID}_i \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$

370

(Equation 3)

371

372 where Effort_{ijk} is the j th observation in complex i for each buffer k , and ComplexID_i is the random
373 intercept, which was assumed to be normally distributed with a mean 0 and variance σ^2 . Two
374 reduced models (“treatment” model and null model) were tested per buffer area to assess the
375 significance of individual terms. The “treatment” model was the full model (Equation 3) including
376 the main effect of Treatment but with the interaction between StatZone and Treatment removed,
377 and the null model removed the Treatment effect entirely. Likelihood ratio tests were performed
378 on the nested models to test for differences at $\alpha = 0.05$ in the removal effect by StatZone
379 and an overall removal effect, respectively. The model in Equation 3 and nested models were fit
380 using the *glmmTMB* package, ver. 1.1.9 (Brooks et al. 2017). Diagnostic tests were performed
381 using the *DHARMA* package, ver. 0.4.6 (Hartig 2022), and contrasts were calculated using the
382 *glht* function in the *multcomp* package, ver. 1.4-26 (Hothorn et al. 2008) in R version 4.4.0 (R
383 Core Team 2024).

384

385 **3. RESULTS**

386 **3.1 Shrimp Fishery Effort**

387 The total shrimping effort per year estimated from the VMS data was relatively constant across
388 the years examined (median 597,488 hours; range 546,765 [2019] to 614,159 [2016] hours;
389 Table 1). The number of vessels participating in the VMS program was also relatively constant
390 (median 42%; range 40% [2015 and 2017] to 47% [2018]; Table 1). The proportion of the
391 shrimp fleet participating in the VMS program increased from 41% (2017) to 47% (2018) as the
392 number of self-reported active shrimp vessels decreased (Smith et al. 2023, Table 1). There
393 was some vessel turnover with approximately 47% of vessels fishing all five years and
394 approximately 10% of vessels only fishing one year.

395

396 Overall, the distribution of shrimp effort across the LA-TX shelf followed distinct patterns partially
397 controlled by the depth of the shelf break (Fig. 1). Near the mouth of the Mississippi River, the
398 shelf is narrow, constraining the fishable bottom and increasing the densities of effort. As the
399 shelf widens west of the Mississippi River, the spatial distribution of shrimp effort spread out,
400 and a bimodal distribution was observed with a distinct nearshore and offshore effort
401 distribution, especially off the Texas coast (StatZones 19-21). An exception to this general
402 pattern was StatZone 21 in which lanes of relatively high effort were observed distributed
403 throughout the depth range (Fig. 1); however, the effort was bimodally distributed across
404 StatZones 19-21 in the months right after the Texas opener (Jul-Aug) and effort shifted closer to
405 shore (SZ 19-20) and consolidated in the latter months of the year (Sep-Dec in SZ 21, Fig. S1).

406

407 Shrimping effort followed a seasonal pattern with low effort across all StatZones in the LA-TX
408 shelf (StatZones 13-21) from Jan-Apr and then increased in StatZones off the Louisiana coast
409 (StatZones 13-16) in May-Jun coinciding with the Texas closure on May 15th (Figs. 2a; see Fig.

410 S2 for individual years). Effort increased in mid-July in the StatZones off of Texas (StatZones
411 17-21) concurrent with the Texas opener on July 15th (Fig. 2a) as effort decreased in the
412 Louisiana StatZones during the same period. The number of vessels per StatZone (and per
413 WEA) per month followed similar patterns to the effort results translating to a relatively constant
414 effort per vessel per StatZone (not shown) per month.

415

416 **3.2 Wind Energy Areas**

417 The area occupied by the WEAs contained about 3.5% of all effort (or about 104,000 hours out
418 of 2,950,000 hours) within the LA-TX shelf (StatZones 13-21) from 2015 to 2019 in federal
419 waters out to the 150 m isobath. The proportion of shrimping effort per StatZone that occurred
420 within the WEAs was low (median 3.7%, range 0.9% to 16.1%), and WEAs within StatZone 18
421 (H, I, and J) had the highest proportion of total shrimping effort per StatZone (16.1%, Table 2).
422 The annual effort within the WEAs was relatively constant (Fig. S2), and the majority of the
423 effort within the proposed WEAs was concentrated in the two largest WEAs (WEAs I and J,
424 Table S1).

425

426 Shrimping effort in the WEAs followed a seasonal pattern (Fig. 2b) consistent with the seasonal
427 effort in the StatZones. For example, effort in the Louisiana WEAs (M and N) was highest in the
428 spring and summer coinciding with the TX closure (Fig. 2b). Then the effort shifted westward
429 into the WEAs in Texas federal waters (A-L) after the Texas opener (Figs. 2b and S4). The
430 number of vessels per WEA per month followed similar patterns to the effort results translating to
431 a relatively constant effort per vessel per WEA (not shown).

432

433 In the areas where leasing is actively occurring or being pursued (RWE Lease Area in WEA M,
434 WEAs C and D as of July 29, 2024), the total VMS effort was about 14,000 hours (or about
435 6700 hrs in RWE lease, 1700 hrs in WEA C, and 6000 hrs in WEA D) from 2015 to 2019. The

436 RWE lease and WEAs C and D only account for 0.5% of the total effort on the LA-TX shelf
437 between 2015 and 2019 (or about 0.02% for RWE, 0.001% for WEA C, and 0.02% for WEA D).

438

439 **3.3 Shrimping Effort Near Rigs**

440 From 2015 to 2019, six rigs were constructed and 585 rigs were removed with 1480 rigs
441 remaining on the LA-TX shelf at the end of 2019. The median distance between rigs not linked
442 by a walkway was 59.2 km (range 10.0 km [StatZone 21] to 77.4 km [StatZone 17]), and the
443 mean nearest neighbor distance was 1.9 km (range 1.0 km [StatZone 13] to 4.1 km [StatZone
444 21]). The median number of rigs per StatZone was 227 (range 3 [StatZone 21] to 508 [StatZone
445 15]) and the StatZones with the highest densities of rigs were offshore Louisiana (SZ 13-16; Fig.
446 1, Table 2). Rigs tended to be distributed across the continental shelf and the median depth
447 distribution was less than 50 m and the depth distribution of rigs tended to be shallower than the
448 depth distribution of shrimping effort per StatZone except for StatZones 20 and 21.

449

450 Total shrimping effort was highest in StatZones 16 and 15 (469,391 hrs and 423,824 hrs,
451 respectively) coinciding with the some of the most rigs (312 and 508, respectively) and some of
452 the greatest densities of rigs per StatZone (1.8 and 3.6 per 100 km² [10x10 km grid],
453 respectively, Table 2).

454

455 On the LA-TX shelf, the cumulative proportion of shrimping effort relative to rigs generally fell
456 into three categories. The first group's cumulative effort, which includes StatZones 13 through
457 17, reached more than 60% within the distance of the horizon (7.6 km, Fig. 3a). These
458 StatZones also had the highest rig densities and some of the highest effort densities (Table 2).
459 Furthermore, considerable spatial overlap existed between rig locations and effort density (Fig
460 1a). The second group, StatZones 18-20, reaches 50% cumulative effort when the top third of
461 the rig was visible from the wheelhouse (24.7 km, Fig. 3a). These StatZones had lower rig

462 densities and lower (SZ 18 and 20) to high (SZ 19) effort densities (Table 2). The spatial overlap
463 of rigs to effort was quite varied for these StatZones (Fig. 1). The overlap was such that lanes of
464 high effort coincided with rigs in StatZone 18, however, in StatZones 19 and 20 there were few
465 rigs and they occurred in areas of relatively low effort. The cumulative effort for StatZone 21
466 differed partially because it never reached 50% when rigs may be visible from the wheelhouse
467 (Fig. 3a). This StatZone was unique because it had multiple lanes of high effort that existed
468 parallel to the shore throughout the depth range (Fig. 1). Only 3 rigs existed in StatZonw 21
469 during the period of study (Table 2). The relationship between buffer area as a proportion of
470 StatZone area to the proportion of effort was nearly linear with minor deviations (Fig. S3), which
471 may suggest that the amount of effort relative to rigs was a function of the space. The
472 interannual variability of the effort in the buffers around rigs was relatively constant with minor
473 variability between years (Fig. S4).

474
475 The derivative of the cumulative proportion of shrimping effort relative to rigs demonstrates that
476 the highest proportion of shrimping effort occurred within distances of 5-10 km of an oil rig (17 to
477 30%, Fig. 3b) in StatZones 13 through 17, which is similar to the distance of the horizon. The
478 proportion of effort in StatZone 18 has a broader peak between 5 km and 12 km. StatZones 19
479 through 21 maximums were 40 km and may be higher beyond that (Fig. 3b), but larger
480 distances were not investigated.

481
482 In StatZones with high densities of rigs (13 through 17), more than 50% of the vessels with VMS
483 had some level of effort within 1 km of a rig. Within 2 km the percentage increases to more than
484 75% (Fig. 3c). The cumulative proportion of vessels near rigs peaked at shorter distances (less
485 than 5 km, Fig. 3c) than the amount of effort spent trawling. For example, for most StatZones,
486 75-100% of vessels were within the horizon distance from the rigs (<7.6 km) while the amount
487 of time spent trawling only reached this level (75-100%) over much greater (15-20 km)

488 distances. For all StatZones, 50% of vessels operating in each StatZone had some effort at
489 distances less than 5 km to the nearest rig (Fig 3c), which was within the distance to the
490 horizon. Generally, the results per StatZone could be classified into two groups categorized by
491 vessels operating off LA and vessels operating off TX (Fig. 3c). The first group off LA had a
492 higher proportion of vessels that had some effort closer to rigs reaching 80% within 5 km. The
493 TX group reached 80% at larger distances (greater than 12 km, Fig. 3c).

494
495 For the rig encounter metric, all StatZones displayed negative encounter values at distances
496 less than the horizon (Fig. 3d). StatZones 13 through 18 displayed minimum values at less than
497 or approximately at the horizon. These minimum values represent decreased rig encounters of
498 about 12% (SZ 13), 13% (SZ 14), 7% (SZ 15), 13% (SZ 16), 4% (SZ 17), and 4% (SZ 18)
499 relative to randomized points (Fig. 3d). Several of these StatZones encounter values became
500 positive at larger distances and reached maximums between 10 and 20 km (4% [SZ 13 and 15],
501 5% [SZ 17], and 9% [SZ 18]; Fig. 3d). Interestingly, the encounter values for StatZones 14, 16,
502 19, and 20 never became positive. The encounter values in StatZone 19 were always negative,
503 having the lowest minimum for all the StatZones at about -32% at 20 km (Fig. 3d). At increasing
504 distances, the rig encounter metric approached zero for most StatZones (13-17 and 21)
505 meaning there was neither attraction nor avoidance at these distances.

506

507 **3.4 Response of Shrimpers to Rigs**

508 Of the six rigs that were constructed during 2015 to 2019 in the study region, three were in 2015
509 (2 in StatZone 14 and 1 in StatZone 17), one was in 2017 (StatZone 16), one was in 2018
510 (StatZone 13), and one was in 2019 (StatZone 15). However, only the rigs constructed in 2017
511 and 2018 were examined more closely because they had effort data in the years pre- and post-
512 construction. For both rigs at 1 km distance, there was zero hours effort pre- and post-
513 construction. For both rigs at 7.5 km distance, there was a reduction of effort from pre-

514 construction to post-construction (191 [2017] and 196 [2018] less hours of shrimping effort, Fig.
515 S5). The proportional reduction, which was the effort in the buffer around the rig constructed
516 divided by the total effort in the StatZone for that year, was on the same order of magnitude
517 between the two years; however, the proportion for 2017 was less than half of the proportion for
518 2018 (0.0021 [2017] versus 0.0050 [2018], Fig. S5).

519

520 From 2015 to 2019, there were a total of 587 rigs removed on the LA-TX shelf in federal waters
521 less than 150 m. A maximum of 182 were removed in 2016 (minimum 76 [2019]). Overall, the
522 the most were removed from StatZone 17 with 140 rigs (minimum 16 [StatZone 20]). For the
523 years 2016 to 2019, there were a total of 400 rigs removed that used as the basis for the linear
524 mixed effects regression. The full 1 km and 7.5 km models had the best fits to the data
525 compared to the nested models (likelihood-ratio tests [LRT], Table 3; see Table S2 & S3 for
526 estimated model parameters, SEs and CIs). There was evidence of an association between
527 effort near rigs and removal at the 1 km level (LRT, p-value = 0.001) but not at the 7.5 km level
528 (LRT, p-value = 0.07). For the 1 km treatment model, the fixed effect coefficient for treatment
529 translates into an estimated 22.8% increase in effort post-removal (95% CI = [8.3%, 39.1%],
530 Fig. 4). For the 7 km treatment model, the fixed effect coefficient for treatment was non-
531 significant (Estimate = -6.3%, 95% CI = [-12.8%, 0.5%], Fig. 4). There was also evidence that
532 the association between effort near rigs and removal varied by StatZone in the 1 km model
533 (LRT, p-value = 0.03) and 7.5 km model (LRT, p-value = 0.006). Model diagnostics found
534 assumptions were adequately met in both the 1 km and 7.5 km models (Figs. S6 & S7,
535 respectively).

536

537 **4. DISCUSSION**

538 The WEAs identified as low conflict areas by the NBSM were developed using large aggregate
539 time scales (e.g., across 5 years). An inspection on more finely resolved annual and monthly

540 time scales further confirmed that the WEAs avoided areas of high shrimping effort. While this
541 study and the NBSM used a time series of only five years, the effort across years was
542 consistent, suggesting some confidence that the results were a fair approximation of the
543 shrimping fleet's expected usage of the LA-TX shelf and the WEAs. If the WEAs are further
544 developed into OSW farms, it is likely that the impacts on the shrimp industry, on the whole, will
545 be relatively minor and primarily on the brown shrimp fishing effort. This study did not
546 distinguish targeted effort between shrimp species due to lack of species information on an
547 equivalent spatial resolution; however, the general distribution of brown shrimp tends to be mid-
548 shelf towards the shelf break (Dettloff 2024; Montero et al. 2016), which overlaps with the
549 location of the WEAs. There could be some impacts on the both brown and white shrimp effort
550 due to the construction of the cables that bring the power onshore. The general distribution of
551 commercial shrimp species (brown and white) in the Gulf is seasonally driven by ontogenetic
552 migration, with juveniles found in estuaries and smaller size classes found nearer to shore
553 (Turner & Brodie, 1983). Broadly, white shrimp reside closer to shore and brown shrimp reside
554 closer to shore during the summer and then shift their distribution mid-shelf to near the shelf
555 break later in the year (Montero et al. 2016).

556
557 While the WEAs largely avoided areas of high shrimping effort, the shrimp fleet usage of these
558 regions varied seasonally and was largely driven by the Texas closure. Shrimping effort
559 increased in the WEAs located on the Louisiana shelf in the months preceding the Texas
560 opener due to spatiotemporal nature of shrimp recruitment out of the estuaries (Turner & Brodie,
561 1983). After the Texas opener, most of the effort shifted to Texas federal waters. There was
562 more effort in WEAs closer to shore in Texas federal waters right after the opener, and then that
563 effort shifts offshore as the fleet chases larger shrimp and nearshore areas become relatively
564 depleted. Because WEA usage varies seasonally, there exists a possibility that a spatial shift of
565 effort could increase fishing pressure to other regions if the WEAs are developed. For example,

566 the WEAs M and N were used more frequently in the months of April and May before the Texas
567 opener; however, if those WEAs were developed and effectively became no longer viable for
568 shrimping, vessels will have to trawl elsewhere. Moreover, hypoxic and anoxic areas expand
569 westward from the Mississippi and Atchafalaya Rivers in the summer months (Morey et al.
570 2003; Rabalais & Turner, 2019). During these events, the shrimp fleet was largely displaced
571 from regions of anoxia, and the fleet trawled the edges of where shrimp may aggregate to
572 escape the hypoxia (Craig and Crowder 2005; Craig et al. 2005; Purcell et al. 2017).
573 Additionally, the Louisiana shelf was host to high densities of rigs, and, if the effort was
574 displaced from active WEA leases, shrimpers may be forced to operate closer to rigs increasing
575 potential conflict between existing offshore industries (e.g., offshore fossil fuel extraction and
576 shipping lanes). While the WEAs currently represent areas not heavily fished, these areas may
577 potentially become prime shrimp habitats in the future increasing interactions between
578 shrimpers and OSW energy infrastructure. Because the shrimp fleet responds dynamically to
579 resource distribution, the fishery is potentially vulnerable to changes to shrimp population
580 redistribution if OSW farms tend to aggregate shrimp distributions.

581
582 In areas with the highest densities of rigs, shrimp vessels trawl primarily at distances within the
583 horizon (e.g., 5 to 7 km). This suggests that the shrimpers may use the rigs as navigation cues
584 in these regions. In regions with high densities of rigs that are primarily on the Louisiana shelf,
585 the trawlable shelf can get narrow eastward toward the Mississippi River. As a result of
586 increasing rig density and decreasing space without rigs, there is a “sweet spot” distance from
587 rigs where shrimpers tend to operate. This result combined with the absence of large areas
588 without rigs explains why the portion of shrimping effort goes to near zero at distances greater
589 than 20 km. To put it another way, there are few trawlable areas that are further than 20 km
590 distant from any rig in StatZones with high rig densities. The Gulf offshore shrimp fishery rely
591 upon a variety of information sources—including visual cues such as navigation lights, radar, and

592 electronic charts to avoid collisions. In the areas with high densities of rigs, there are also
593 pipelines, submarine wellheads, and other vessels, including shrimpers actively trawling
594 (Anderson et al. 1949; Scott-Denton et al. 2012). As a result, adequate space to maneuver can
595 be limited, necessitating optimal distances at which shrimping operations are likely to occur near
596 static infrastructure. The patterns of effort near rigs differed on the Texas shelf due to a
597 combination of fewer rigs and a wider continental shelf allowing the fleet to spread out.
598 Interestingly, most vessels throughout the study region had some effort within a few kilometers
599 of rigs in areas with relatively high and low rig densities. The pattern suggests shrimp vessel
600 operators were comfortable trawling near these structures or did so out of necessity. While
601 shrimpers avoided rigs at smaller distances within the horizon, there seemed to be a preference
602 for areas at larger distances (e.g., 7.5 to 20 km) from rigs. This was likely due to the coincidence
603 of where shrimp were found and where rigs are located. Thus, shrimpers may avoid rigs as
604 navigational hazards but are generally prefer the same areas due to the spatial overlap of the
605 two industries' interests. The Texas shelf was different than that of Louisiana because there was
606 not the same overlap of shrimping effort and rigs off Texas making it more difficult to infer a
607 behavioral response.

608
609 Shrimping effort increased on small spatial scales (1 km) after rigs were removed from an area,
610 but not at larger spatial scales (7.5 km). The significant shift at 1 km suggests a localized
611 response where shrimpers were likely moving short distances into these areas the year after
612 rigs were removed. The lack of a response in shrimping effort due to rig removal at the larger
613 spatial scale of 7.5 km was likely due to the observed peak in effort between distances of 5 to 7
614 km. This optimal operating distance would be invariant to rig removal or if anything might have a
615 negative response (decreasing effort at the larger scale) as vessels moved into areas that were
616 previously avoided on smaller spatial scales (in fact the response at 7.5 km was negative but
617 non-significant). As the results of this study have demonstrated, shrimping effort around rigs on

618 the LA-TX shelf occurred in distinct patterns. It is difficult to attribute a behavioral response by
619 shrimpers to structures from a purely analytical perspective without direct knowledge of vessel
620 operator decision-making. On the other hand, it is likely that shrimpers were responding to rigs
621 during fishing operations, especially in areas that have high densities of rigs and high densities
622 of shrimping effort. The spacing between wind turbines is a tradeoff between generating enough
623 power to be profitable and adherence to offshore safety guidelines, but the distance will likely be
624 approximately 1 nmi apart (~1.9 km, Mulas-Hernando et al. 2023). It is difficult to predict if
625 shrimpers will trawl in areas with high density of structures because individual operators'
626 tolerance to risk exists on a spectrum with unknown variability. There are notable differences in
627 the layout of rigs engaging in fossil fuel extraction (non-random, clusters of rigs) versus offshore
628 wind farms (regular spacing between turbines), and thus, shrimpers will respond differently to
629 these industries. Most shrimpers will likely avoid trawling in areas with high structure density
630 given the restricted ability to maneuver; however, some shrimpers may try to “thread the needle”
631 between closely spaced structures as observed in the VMS data in areas of high rig densities.
632

633 Overall, our analyses demonstrate the complex seascape shrimpers must navigate to avoid
634 collisions and successfully conduct trawl operations. Each vessel operator (i.e., captain or crew
635 standing watch) will likely have a “sweet spot” distance in which they feel comfortable trawling
636 near a rig while additionally considering other factors, such as the proximity and density of other
637 vessels (fishing or non-fishing), environmental conditions (e.g., visibility, rain, wind, or wave
638 height), time of day (crepuscular versus nighttime trawling), fatigue of vessel operators, and
639 other unknown factors. The maneuvering requirements of a shrimp vessel will also influence the
640 distance between the shrimp vessel and offshore infrastructure. With trawl nets deployed, a
641 shrimp vessel is restricted in its ability to maneuver meaning that turning requires a large radius
642 to avoid tangling the nets or capsizing the vessel. The typical offshore shrimp vessel uses two
643 double rigs for a total of 4 trawl nets that have an operational spread of 45 to 60 meters

644 (GMFMC, 2005). Furthermore, the rule of thumb is that for a given depth of water, a captain will
645 let out 3 to 5 times the length of cable to optimally engage in shrimp trawling (Pereyra, 1963).
646 Taken together, this means that distance between obstacles and depth are factors in
647 maneuverability and influence vessel operators in finding a “sweet spot” distance from offshore
648 infrastructure during shrimp trawling operations.

649
650 The shrimping effort within the WEAs represents a small fraction of the total shrimping effort on
651 the LA-TX shelf; however, this potential loss of fishable ground may disproportionately affect
652 certain vessels or ports. Methods to derive VMS effort estimates on the scale of individual tows
653 are ongoing. Once these data become available, a finer-scale analysis that examines which
654 vessels and ports are most likely to be impacted by OSW development in the WEAs could
655 assist in identifying the most heavily impacted communities. This information could then be used
656 to target stakeholder engagement and fishery compensation funds. These details would provide
657 valuable context to better understand how WEAs may impact individual vessels. We did not
658 explore the impacts that WEAs may have on transit between LA and TX, especially in response
659 to the TX closure. This is relevant as the WEAs occupy regions that sit between productive
660 shrimping grounds in LA and TX. While the WEAs are generally expected to be open to transit,
661 even if they are effectively fishing exclusion zones, there may be some displacement during
662 construction or decommissioning. As profits can be constrained by fluctuating prices of fuel and
663 ex-vessel prices for shrimp, increasing transit times may have the effect of displacing effort to
664 keep costs roughly stable between years. Fishing footprints are dynamic and are likely to
665 change as environmental and socioeconomic conditions change in the future.

666
667 The penaeid shrimp fishery on the LA-TX shelf continues to be an economically and culturally
668 significant part of life in the U.S. Gulf Coast (Griffith et al. 2023). The distribution of shrimp
669 populations is a major influence on the decision to allocate shrimping effort. On smaller spatio-

670 temporal scales, several factors influence shrimper effort allocation, including bottom suitability
671 (areas without large obstructions), prior knowledge of productive shrimping grounds, the
672 seascape as perceived from the wheelhouse (rigs, other vessels, and fairways), and the
673 distribution of the target species assessed by individual shrimpers in real-time. Individual
674 decision-making is also affected by macroeconomic forces such as the global shrimp supply
675 and ex-vessel prices in addition to the price of consumables such as diesel fuel and food (Liese
676 & Travis, 2010). Each of these factors operates at different spatio-temporal scales and
677 contributes to the decision-making process used to select where and when a shrimper will
678 allocate effort. However, localized differences in shrimp density on daily time scales are likely
679 most influential to effort allocation as shrimpers employ a smaller trawl net, called a try net, to
680 more frequently sample potential shrimping areas and assess catch per unit effort in real-time
681 (GMFMC, 1981). Thus the fleet responds dynamically to resource distribution making the fishery
682 potentially vulnerable to changes to shrimp population redistribution especially in the context of
683 new multi-use activities in the Gulf (e.g., OSW).

684
685 Rigs are known to act as areas of high biodiversity and high biomass; however, there is a robust
686 debate around the relative attraction versus production potential of artificial reefs such as rigs
687 (Pickering & Whitmarsh, 1997; Cowan et al. 1999; Layman & Allgeier, 2020; Czaja Jr. et. al, *in*
688 *review*). In reality, both mechanisms are operating as substrate-limited species will settle on
689 available surfaces attracting more settlement, which then attracts mobile, higher trophic level
690 species. It is not known to what degree commercially important shrimp species are attracted or
691 avoidant to structures such as oil rigs. Being that shrimps are benthic and spend time buried in
692 mud, it is possible that commercial shrimp species are neutral toward structure, or because
693 shrimps are a common prey species, they are less abundant near structure, as high rates of
694 predation may act to decrease abundance (Reeds et al. 2018).

695

696 As new marine spatial uses, like OSW, mature in the region, additional research is needed to
697 better understand how the fishery and other activities may be affected by increased vessel
698 traffic, new structure, and the potential for spatiotemporal closures (temporary or permanent)
699 (Sura et.al, *in review*). The NBSM identified 14 WEA options by spatially weighting multiple data
700 layers including areas of “high” shrimping effort (4.5 days per year or more, Randall et al. 2022).
701 The results of the NBSM produced several spatial blocks that may not be practical for the
702 offshore commercial shrimp fishery. For example, WEA option I has several ‘cutouts’ that are
703 recommended to be removed from consideration for OSW development. These ‘cutouts’ are
704 areas of higher shrimp effort and serve to deconflict multi-use in the region (Randall et al. 2022).
705 Additionally, several WEAs, including WEA I with the ‘cutouts’, are adjacent to a major shipping
706 fairway leading into Galveston Bay. Our work has shown that shrimpers rely heavily on visual
707 cues to inform navigation and these ‘cutouts’, which are 4.8 km wide, may not be utilized by
708 shrimpers once they are surrounded on three sides by OSW infrastructure in addition to being
709 bounded by shipping fairways. Additional information on turning radius during trawling and
710 consultation with active shrimpers would help address potential limitations of these ‘cutouts’ and
711 could be used to design realistic concessions suited to the shrimp fishery. The results of the
712 suitability modeling, which included aggregate shrimp VMS data into a presence/absence of
713 “high” effort, have initially proven to be successful as major stakeholders, such as the Southern
714 Shrimp Alliance, seem broadly satisfied by the placement of the WEAs (SSA, 2022); however,
715 finer details on transmission lines are currently lacking as of February 2025. Our work suggests
716 that some of the MSP decisions based on shrimping effort data may not be practical once
717 applied. Future spatial modeling efforts may want to consider the use of a visual buffer
718 threshold, higher-resolution VMS data, and individual vessel behavior and maneuverability.
719
720 The introduction of MSP methods to the Gulf offshore renewable energy siting and development
721 processes represents a shift from the traditional approach to ONG infrastructure siting. Previous

722 approaches in the region, which focused primarily on single-sectoral concerns (Smythe &
723 McCann, 2019), have shifted to multi-sectoral, ecosystem-conscious approaches representing a
724 more holistic process. Historically, ONG infrastructure was positioned based on immediate
725 access and availability to oil and gas deposits, meaning that potential conflicts with other
726 sectors were rarely considered, which begets the need for a more considerate and inclusive
727 approach. While commercial shrimp fisheries have been included in environmental impact
728 statements for ONG leasing in the Gulf and individual leases may have minimal impacts
729 (BOEM, 2017), the cumulative impacts are trending toward some industries being excluded due
730 to insufficient space to operate. The novel application of MSP in the Gulf through the NBSM
731 holds considerable promise for the deconfliction of potentially competing sectors, represented
732 as layers in the spatial model, particularly for emerging industries like OSW. This new approach,
733 which does have caveats as mentioned above, considers and theoretically optimizes economic
734 viability for OSW and mitigates interactions between infrastructure, human activities, and natural
735 resources.

736

737 In the Northeast US and mid-Atlantic, where MSP methods like the NBSM were not used for
738 initial OSW siting, managers are navigating considerable stakeholder pushback on existing and
739 planned projects related to multi-sectoral conflict. Though some processes used in these
740 regions accounted for existing ocean uses and spatial information (example: Commercial
741 Leasing for Wind Power on the Outer Continental Shelf in the New York Bight—Call for
742 Information and Nominations, Federal Register, Vol. 83, Num. 70, 2018), the siting methods
743 used in the Northeast and mid-Atlantic were much less robust than the NBSM used in the Gulf.
744 The resulting projects have faced fierce opposition based on coastal and landscape aesthetic
745 damage, inadequate biological surveying, and conflict with commercial and recreational fishing
746 (Sokoloski et al., 2018). While some opposition does exist in the Gulf - and it should be noted
747 that the Gulf has an extensive history of stakeholder engagement in the offshore energy siting

748 process (Priest, 2016) - early feedback from stakeholders and special interest groups (like the
749 Southern Shrimp Alliance) suggests that the spatial modeling approach may lead to increased
750 satisfaction with siting activities (SSA, 2022).

751
752 By examining shrimper's response to rigs as surrogates for wind farms, this study provides
753 some insight into the dynamics between two existing offshore industries operating in a shared
754 spatial domain. There are many unknowns in how the wind industry will impact existing fisheries
755 but the strength of this study is the data-driven approach to understanding interactions between
756 industries. The study had several caveats that limit the broader application of the methods and
757 results to predict interactions between the shrimp industry and offshore wind farms. Rigs are
758 imperfect surrogates because they are spatially distributed more heterogeneously. Individual
759 turbines in windfarms will be regularly spaced producing a different seascape than currently
760 encountered by shrimp vessels in the Gulf. Furthermore, the use of rig removals instead of
761 construction is less ideal to infer a response to construction because construction will likely
762 cause an immediate response as space is occupied. Whereas after decommissioning and rig
763 removal there is likely a lagged response as shrimpers may be wary of unknown obstacles on
764 the seafloor in addition to some other unquantified behavioral response. In reality, a nearly
765 100% reduction in effort due to wind farm construction is likely on small spatial scales especially
766 when we consider that the regular nature of wind turbine spacing will likely act as trawling
767 exclusion zones. Additionally, consideration of the spatial distribution of shrimp on patterns in
768 shrimping effort, better information on the inshore (non-federally permitted) component of the
769 fleet, and the potential effect of ancillary structures associated with oil rigs and/or OSWs (e.g.,
770 pipelines) is needed. Despite these limitations, our analysis provides a fine-scale understanding
771 of how shrimp vessels navigate the complex seascape to effectively engage in shrimp trawling.

772

773 Regardless of planning and eventual siting, the increasing density of maritime activities and
774 structures necessitates closer proximity between people and marine infrastructure. Without an
775 increase in the rate of decommissioning of existing structures, the overall amount of ‘untouched’
776 ocean will inevitably decrease. With the anticipated expansion of the blue economy, new marine
777 spatial uses—including OSW, offshore hydrogen production, and aquaculture—mean that
778 ocean space will become increasingly contested. The Gulf shrimp VMS data provides a fine-
779 scale perspective on the region’s most valuable fishery and should be used in future to support
780 the continuity of the shrimp fishery as multiple industries vie for space in the region.

781

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796

797 **CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT**

798 The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

799

800 **DATA AVAILABILITY**

801 Platform database is publicly accessible on the BOEM website

802 (<https://www.data.boem.gov/Platform/PlatformStructures/Default.aspx>). The WEA shapefile may

803 be request from the NOAA-NCCOS Marine and Coastal Planning division

804 (<https://coastalscience.noaa.gov/science-areas/coastal-and-marine-planning/>). The shrimp VMS

805 data are confidential and cannot be released.

806

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812

813 **ETHICS STATEMENT**

814 To the best of our knowledge, our work and practices fully comply with the ethics guidelines set

815 by this journal and general scientific and academic standards.

816

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1111 **TABLES**

1112

1113 **Table 1.** Annual summary of VMS data, “Proportion VMS” corresponds to the number of active
 1114 shrimping vessels with VMS units divided by the total active federally permitted shrimp vessels.

Year	Total effort (hours)	Total VMS vessels	Total vessels	Proportion VMS
2015	602,435	409	1,012	0.40
2016	614,159	422	1,015	0.42
2017	597,488	413	1,009	0.41
2018	588,446	452	963	0.47
2019	546,765	403	911	0.44

1115

1116

1117 **Table 2.** Summary of active ONG Rigs, VMS effort, and WEA distribution sorted by Stat Zone.
 1118 Shading in the table is conditional based on data quartiles in each column (i.e., first, second,
 1119 third, and fourth quartile).

StatZone	StatZone area (km ²)	Rigs per StatZone	Rig density (1/100 km ²)	Median rig nearest neighbor (km)	Median rig distance (km)	Total VMS Effort 2015-2019 (hrs)	Effort density (hr/km ²)	WEAs within SZ	SZ Effort Proportion within WEA
13	4,113	227	5.52	0.96	32.7	194,431	47.3	0	N/A
14	9,730	396	4.07	0.98	46.3	298,860	30.7	0	N/A
15	14,181	508	3.58	1.15	59.8	423,824	29.9	0	N/A
16	17,375	312	1.80	1.73	74.6	469,391	27.0	1	0.01
17	19,683	263	1.34	2.11	77.0	346,716	17.6	4	0.05
18	15,407	79	0.51	2.68	69.7	291,347	18.9	3	0.16
19	8,799	42	0.48	1.88	59.2	315,707	35.9	5	0.08
20	12,178	23	0.19	3.64	49.3	233,936	19.2	2	0.01
21	7,658	3	0.04	4.13	10.0	375,049	49.0	1	0.02

1120 *StatZones 17 and 18 share WEA option J

1121 **StatZones 19 and 20 share WAE option C

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1125 **Table 3.** Likelihood ratio tests for the 1km and 7.5km removal models. Tweedie power
 1126 parameter (ρ) is given in parentheses for each model.

Model Formula							
Full model	<i>Effort ~ StatZone + TotalEffortSZ + Treatment + StatZone * TotalEffortSZ + StatZone * Treatment + (1 ComplexID)</i>						
Treatment model	<i>Effort ~ StatZone + TotalEffortSZ + Treatment + StatZone * TotalEffortSZ + (1 ComplexID)</i>						
Reduced model	<i>Effort ~ StatZone + TotalEffortSZ + StatZone * TotalEffortSZ + (1 ComplexID)</i>						
1 km scale	df	AIC	LogLik	Deviance	χ^2	df	p-value
Reduced ($\rho=1.46$)	19	3798.5	-1880.3	3760.5			
Treatment ($\rho=1.46$)	20	3790.2	-1875.1	3750.2	10.33	1	0.001
Full ($\rho=1.44$)	27	3789	-1867.5	3735	15.18	7	0.034
7.5 km scale	df	AIC	LogLik	Deviance	χ^2	df	p-value
Reduced ($\rho=1.43$)	19	12113	-6037.6	12075			
Treatment ($\rho=1.43$)	20	12112	-6036	12072	3.26	1	0.071
Full ($\rho=1.44$)	27	12232	-6026	12052	19.98	7	0.006

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1128 FIGURES
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 1131 **Figure 1.** Spatial domain of the VMS data used in this analysis, overlaid with information about
 1132 active and removed ONG rigs from 2015-2019 and Gulf Statistical Zones (top), and the
 1133 distribution of Gulf WEA Options identified by the NCCOS/BOEM Suitability Model, the RWE
 1134 Lease and the Hecate Noncompetitive Lease Request (bottom). Total shrimping effort in hours
 1135 trawled from 2015-2019 is displayed on both top and bottom maps. The boundary of the Texas
 1136 federal waters is displayed in blue indicating where shrimping is prohibited during the annual
 1137 Texas closure.

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 1139 **Figure 2.** The plots display seasonal patterns of median shrimp effort density (hours/km²) per
 1140 StatZone (a) and per WEA (b). Boxplots display the monthly effort densities (hours/km²) per
 1141 StatZone (c) and WEA (d). Gray bars represent the timing of the Texas closure (May 15 - July
 1142 15). Note the ranges of the ordinate axes differ between the top and bottom panels.

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 1144 **Figure 3.** Results from the buffer analysis displaying the cumulative proportion of shrimping
 1145 effort (a) and vessels (c) as a function of distance from ONG rig. The proportion of shrimping
 1146 effort (b) is the derivative of the cumulative proportion of effort. The inset map in subplot (c) is a
 1147 color key indicating which color denotes which StatZone. (d) Rig encounter metric per StatZone
 1148 from random points analysis. Negative values denote a reduction of effort relative to
 1149 randomization and positive values indicate increased effort. The white-to-gray regions indicate
 1150 distances that rigs are fully to partially visible from the wheelhouse of a shrimp vessel. The lines
 1151 (from left to right) are the horizon at 7.6 km, partially visible at 24.7 km, and not visible at 31.8
 1152 km. The white-to-gray regions indicate distances that rigs are fully to partially visible from the
 1153 wheelhouse of a shrimp vessel. The division between regions (from left to right) are the horizon
 1154 at 7.6 km, partially visible- or when the upper two-thirds are visible at 21.6 km, and not visible at
 1155 31.8 km.

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Figure 4. Effect of rig removal on VMS effort by StatZone for both buffer distances. The overall effect is on the far righthand side of the plot separated by a thick, vertical black line. Values are model estimated percent changes in shrimping effort after rig removal with 95% confidence intervals (CI) based on the 1 km and 7.5 km generalized linear mixed models. A dashed, horizontal black line at 0 denotes no change in effort due to rig removals. Significance at $\alpha=0.05$ can be inferred if the CI does not cross the line at zero.